

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B505		
Date:	29/01/10		
Take Off:	07:56:55Z	Z	Z
Landing:	13:18:33Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	5h 21m 38s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: CONSTRAIN

Operating Area: North Atlantic/ NW Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
2	Co	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Robbie Voden	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester Uni
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM
8	CVI / Mission Scientist Training	Kirsty McBeath	Met Office
9	Mini-LIDAR	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester Uni
11	Mission 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
12	Mission 3	Paul Barratt	Met Office
13	SID-2 / SID-3	Joseph Ulanowski	Hertfordshire Uni
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
Y	Pre-flight log
Y	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
Y	Screengrabs (Weather Radar)
	Planning charts or plots
Y	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2010-01-29	Alan Woolley	Initial version
R1			
r2			

b505 07:37:48-13:19:29

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B505

Date:29/1/10

Project:CONSTRAIN

Location:North Atlantic/Lewis

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
074725		startup	0.47 kft	081	
075436		taxy	0.48 kft	120	
075655		T/O	0.46 kft	301	
082510		wrxr pc clock	20.0 kft	347	on time
091215	092850	Profile 1	19.9 - 0.35 kft	035	
092901	093358	Run 1	0.41 - 0.43 kft	332	
093539	094105	Run 2	0.89 - 0.93 kft	124	
094756	095527	Run 3	7.5 - 7.3 kft	205	
095527	095640	Profile 2	7.3 - 8.3 kft	306	
095647	100255	Run 4	8.3 kft	230	
100801	100942	Run 5	9.3 kft	305	
101216	101404	Run 6	9.3 kft	110	
101719	101906	Run 7	9.3 kft	322	
102226	102426	Run 8	9.3 kft	135	
102712	103142	Run 9	9.3 kft	325	
103535	103818	Run 10	9.8 kft	134	
104120	104440	Run 11	10.3 kft	326	
104738	105000	Run 12	10.3 kft	158	
110929	111030	Run 13	3.4 kft	186	
111031	111128	Profile 3	3.4 - 4.4 kft	177	
111129	112041	Run 14	4.4 - 4.3 kft	184	
112405	112610	Run 15	4.3 - 4.4 kft	305	
112939	113136	Run 16	5.3 - 5.4 kft	137	
113637	114216	Run 17	6.4 kft	326	
114532	115240	Run 18	7.4 kft	121	
114604		qnh stornaway	7.4 kft	138	1000mb
115537	120203	Run 19	8.4 kft	316	
120610	121026	Run 20	9.4 kft	126	
121319	121610	Run 21	9.9 kft	309	
121925	122242	Run 22	9.9 - 9.8 kft	118	
122639	123010	Profile 4	10.0 - 7.4 kft	329	interrupt
123542	123747	Profile 5	10.0 - 8.3 kft	140	
124027	124213	Profile 5	8.3 - 6.5 kft	351	

124349	124532	Profile 5	6.4 - 5.0 kft	138
131833		Land	0.46 kft	303 Prestwick

B505, 29 Jan 2010 CONSTRAIN FLIGHT 10

Sortie S5: Ice nucleation and secondary ice multiplication in super-cooled Cumulus.

Super-cooled Cumulus are required for observations of mixed-phase studies, where ice nucleation, secondary ice multiplication and warm-rain processes are important.

Secondary ice multiplication from splintering during the riming growth of ice particles is active between -3°C and -8°C .

Both the intensity and duration of surface precipitation depends on warm-rain processes (auto-conversion of cloud liquid) and ice-phase processes.

Weather

Sortie location

Northwest – Stornaway, with option of NE

Sortie summary

Sample a growing Cumulus with a series of ascending straight and level runs.

Alternatively, if there are many Cumulus, sample each by a series of long straight and level runs at specified altitudes.

Cloud penetrations should allow at least 60sec wings level before entering and after leaving cloud to allow for aerosol characterisation

Sortie detail

- 1) **Transit** to operating area at best-range speed and altitude.
- 2) Identify Cumulus generating region.
- 3) **Profile descent** (stepped to stay in region, avoiding cloud penetrations) to reach minimum altitude below target clouds.
- 4) **Aerosol characterisation run** 500ft below cloud base, remaining in inflow-region of target clouds.
- 5) Ascend to 0°C level ($\sim 3\text{kft}$) and identify growing cumulus.
- 6) **Cloud penetration runs:** Starting at 0°C level, perform a series of straight and level runs through the cloud, ascending during the turns so that each run is 500ft below cloud top. Alternatively, penetrate a series of Cumulus (7).
- 7) **Many cloud alternative:** Long straight and level runs at constant altitude, deviating to penetrate each cloud. Altitudes are from 0°C to -20°C , in particular in the Hallet-Mossop regime -3°C to -8°C .
- 8) **Drop a Sonde** Climb to 5kft above cloud top and drop a sonde *or* (9)
- 9) **Stepped Profile Descent through cloud** in a stairwell-fashion profile descent with cloud penetrations at similar altitudes as those on ascent
- 10) **Land at Stornaway** for refuel.
- 11) **Repeat from (2)** Sampling developing Cu
- 12) **Transit to Prestwick at best range speed and altitude**

Instrument requirements

Lidar

CVI operated continuously in Counter-Flow mode, except for the sub-cloud run which is in aerosol mode.

Cloud physics to report the time when first ice particles are observed during each of the cloud penetration runs.

Crew:

1. Captain - Luc Lathouwers (Directflight)
2. Co-pilot - Alan Foster (Directflight)
3. CCM - Robbie Voaden (Directflight)
4. Mission Scientist - Keith Bower (University of Manchester)
5. Flight Manager - Alan Woolley (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics - Martyn Pickering (Met Office)
7. AVAPS – Core Chemistry - Doug Anderson (FAAM)
8. Mini-LIDAR / FWVS - Dave Pollard (Met Office)
9. CVI - Kirsty McBeath (Met Office)
10. SID2 / SID3 - Joseph Ulanowski (University of Hertfordshire)
11. Manchester Cloud - James Dorsey (University of Manchester)
12. Mission Scientist 2 - Richard Cotton (Met Office)
13. Mission Scientist 3 – Paul Barrett (Met Office)

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 29.01.10

Flight No: B 505

Pre-Flighter: STEVE COWAN

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
1	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Pos for 79 142
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Enter cyl content press	N ₂ = 89 bar CO ₂ /Ar = 138 bar
3	✓	Core Chemistry	Driers OK	instruments checked on way to Post flight
4		Cabin	All Racks Checked	
5	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
6	✓	Core Chemistry	All Flows Checked OK	
7	✓	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
8	✓	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
16	✓	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
17	✓	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
19	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
20	✓	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
22	✓	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
23	✓	Satcom C	Checked	In cockpit
24	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
25	✗	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	✗	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	✗	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	✗	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
29	✗	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
30	✗	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
31	✗	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
32	✓	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
33	✗	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
34	✗	3786 CPC	Drained	
35	✗	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
36	✓	Core Chemistry	O ₃ /NO _x /CO zeros performed Ok	
<u>External Checks</u>				
37	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
38	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
39	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
40	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
41	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
42	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
43	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
44	✗	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
45	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
46	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
47		TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
48		All other covers	Removed	
49		Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
50		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
51		Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
52		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
53		ICEX applied		
54		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

GMT	Profile	Height	Time	Position	Notes
0758					T/D
08400		20ft		57.5 SW	solid Sc, Cu deck below RADAR range about 40 miles to 80 miles - sample found on
08500					-1° @ surface
0857					Heading West to find clearer slot
0906					Heading North to find development Cu.
091300					RADAR range set to 40 miles still searching for cloud, wind $\angle = 343^\circ$
	A				Can ask for profile through clear slot
					LIDAR - Top ~ 5000 (South) Top ~ 11000 (North)
					Profile descends through clear slot
0914					Through stratified layers @ 9.54Z fasten descent 2kft min ⁻¹ to stay in clear air

Mission Scientist's Log ³

Flight No **B.55** Date 29.01.12 Name PARRETT Page 2 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					inside cloud base 5kt → 25ft
					Precep to 40ft - photos
					cloud base ~ 24ft
					Scud below ~ 1.34ft
					→ 1.04ft
					PCAP ~ 30 PCAP-CU ~ 20 ✓
					CPC-air ~ 100, spike to ~ 400
					red or shattering
0954					First 400m altimeter
					just before now
0955 24					just done
0956			1		
1000 31					Near saturation
					begin to enter cloud
1002					climbing to 990 to intercept
					cloud.
					passing through other clouds in the
					way
					PADA range altered to 20m
					hubs probe iced up
					↳ ~ 30°
1003 30		in Run			$T_a = -19.7$
1005 51					$T_d \sim$ similar
10.15					Alt = 9.34ft
					cond icing

Mission Scientist's Log } 3

Flight No **B505**... Date **29-01-10** Name **P. BARRETT**... Page **4** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				S01 G	spotted possible cloud ahead
					going in cloud @ ~ 340ft
					turboprobe on the way back
110929	13	334ft		S042, S54	Not in cloud base
1111	14	4.24ft		S036, S54	- in some cloud, turning to right to
					Ant man
					All liquid, T = -8 T _f = -9.8
1116					Flying across wind through a cloud
					snowy section,
					visually spst particles
					mostly ice

Mission Scientist's Log 3

Flight No **B** ^{Sus} Date ²⁹⁻⁰¹⁻¹⁰ ~~2-1-10~~ Name **P. BARRETT** Page **5** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1125					identified dark work all liquid
112939	16	5.3	N-S	58N, 65W	run into cloud base @ ~4-5 kft turning onto with fly @ 327, blue streaks rising N-S
1137	→ into cloud				30 wind direction ice at the end of the cloud dark
					11:37 →
1142:20					out of cloud, distance 7 cloud was ~6 minutes across
	18				
1151					out of cloud of the beginning under edge ✓
115644		8.3	330		in cloud - into wind at low end of cloud
		9.3			in cloud tops now, next run will drop 500ft

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B505

Date: 29 Jan 10

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC only
2. Aft Console Ethernet rearranged owing to problem on rack switch
- 3.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom

MPDS – 2 x satpics

Satcom H – not used

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Cloud Physics Flight Log B505

Date:29/01/2010	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:06:00:00	DAU1 Time:same	DAU2 Time:same	AUX1 Time:same	AUX2 Time:same
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2+SID3		2DC	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	3.14	Vref (>7V):	7.8	El#1 V (>1):	0.86	El#1 V (>1):	4.72	Comms2?:	y	El#1 V (>1):	-2.2
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.18	El#32 V (>1):	2.54	El#32 V (>1):	2.92	Comms2?:	Y	El#32 V (>1):	-2.0
			Sheath flow	14.15	El#64 V (>1)	1.32	El#64 V (>1)	1.95				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
06:18:05			15									
06:19:37			20									
06:20:56			30									
06:22:38			40									
06:24:09				ZERO								
09:12:16	FL200			10							Noise	Start Profile 1
09:13:02	FL190			10								
09:13:59	FL180			10								
09:14:49	FL170			7								
09:15:46	FL160			8								
09:18:31	FL130			35								
09:19:35	FL120			50								
09:20:02	FL110			50								
09:21:01	FL100			25								
09:21:53	FL090			75								
09:22:43	FL080			50								

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
09:23:53	FL070			45								
09:24:46	FL040			60								
09:25:09	FL030			70								
09:25:40	FL020			60								
09:26:53	FL010			35							Noise	
09:28:49	50'			45								End of Profile
09:28:55	100'											Start Run 1
09:29:00				40								
09:31:00				40								
09:33:00				45								
09:33:54												End of Run
09:35:34	500'											Start Run 2
09:36:00				35								
09:38:00				35		0.0004		0.5	800	8		
09:41:05												End of Run
09:47:53	FL074											Start Run 3
09:48:00				30								
09:50:00		15	27	500		0.07		45	800	8	900	
09:52:00		1	15	300		0.05		125	800	8	100	
09:54:00		10	30	300		0.0001		500	400	1	800	
09:55:26	FL074											End of Run & Start Profile 2
09:56:43	FL083											End of Profile & Start Run 4
09:57:00				20								
09:59:00				10								
10:01:00		20	30	1000				1000	250	1	1000	
10:02:57												End of Run
10:07:46	FL092											Start Run 5
10:08:00				25								
10:09:40												End of Run
10:12:14	FL092											Start Run 6
10:13:30		40	35	30				30	50	12	1000	
10:14:04												End of Run
10:17:12	FL092											Start Run 7
10:18:00		25	35	40		0.01		500	25	12	800	
10:19:06												End of Run
10:22:24	FL093											Start Run 8

Cloud Physics Flight Log B505

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
10:23:00				30								
10:24:24												End of Run
10:27:12	FL093											Start Run 9
10:28:00				25								
10:30:00		15	20	500		0.15		500	800	8	500	
10:31:37												End of Run
10:35:30	FL098											Start Run 10
10:36:00				10				300	300	8		
10:38:00		5	35	75		0.05		20	400	8	100	
10:38:17												End of Run
10:41:19	FL103											Start Run 11
10:42:00												
10:44:00		0.5	45	70		0.02		350	600	8	100	
10:44:40												End of Run
10:47:39	FL103											Start Run 12
10:48:00				30								
10:50:00												End of Run
11:09:29	FL033											Start Run 13
11:10:30	FL033											End of Run & Start Profile 3
11:11:20	FL043											End of Profile & Start Run 14
11:12:00		2.5	17	50		0.0001		1			200	
11:14:00				35								
11:16:00				30								
11:18:00				45		0.1		300	800	8	1	
11:20:38												End of Run
11:24:05	FL043											Start Run 15
11:25:00		3	20	30				1			50	
11:26:09												End of Run
11:29:39	FL053											Start Run 16
11:30:00		3	32	40		0.0002		5	300	1	400	
11:31:40												End of Run
11:36:35	FL063											Start Run 17
11:37:00		5	37	90		0.002		600	100	12	700	
11:39:00				30		0.04		160	800	8	10	
11:41:00		0.1	15	50		0.06		250	800	8	10	
11:42:16												End of Run

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	CIP15	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/L	Max R			
11:45:33	FL073											Start Run 18
11:46:00				25								
11:48:00		0.01	10	25		0.01		60	800	8	10	
11:50:00		2	10	40		0.01		400	750	8	100	
11:52:00		25	35	30		0.01		135	400	1	100	
11:52:40	FL073											End of Run
11:55:29	FL083											Start Run 19
11:56:00				35								
11:58:00		20	40	110		0.1		300	800	8	200	
12:00:00				10		0.025		110	650	8	10	
12:02:05												End of Run
12:06:01	FL093											Start Run 20
12:07:00				5		0.025		50	500	8	10	
12:09:00				40		0.01		35	800	8	10	
12:10:20												End of Run
12:13:14	FL098											Start Run 21
12:14:00				5								
12:16:00				8								
12:16:08												End of Run
12:19:26	FL098											Start Run 22
12:20:00												
12:22:00						0.01		8	600	8		
12:22:40												End of Run
12:26:36	FL099			3								Start Profile 4
12:27:46	FL080											
12:29:55	FL073			8								End of Profile
12:35:42	FL100			6								Start Profile 5
12:36:45	FL090			6		0.001		10	550	10	90	
12:40:45	FL080	4	20	70		0.04		140	800	8	60	
12:41:51	FL070			25								
12:44:16	FL060	1	45	300		0.15		400	800	8	10	
12:45:32	FL050			45								End of Profile

0730 on Fri 29 Jan

0830 on Fri 29 Jan

0900 on Fri 29 Jan

1000 on Fri 29 Jan

1100 on Fri 29 Jan

1200 on Fri 29 Jan

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 0700 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 0800 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 0900 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 29 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 29 Jan 2010 0900UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 29 Jan 2010 1000 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 29 Jan 2010 1100 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 29 Jan 2010 1200 UTC

WEATHER

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

Map

Range: 5

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

Map

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
Map

Range: 5
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 40

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

20

40

60

80

Range: 80
STABILIZATION FAULT
Gain: Max
WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

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Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

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Range: 80

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Gain: Max
WX

Range: 80

STABILIZATION FAULT

Gain: Max

WX

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